

Averaging Over Time and the Uncertainty Principle in Quantum And Classical Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 27, 2018

It is possible to have an average which exists almost instantaneously in time, but one can also have averages which are computed over a time interval. It was argued in previous notes that average kinetic energy in quantum mechanics is one such average computed over time, as a particle in a potential scatters from one plane wave state to another. The frequency for this process is E from $\exp(iEt)$, the time dependent part of the wavefunction.

If this is the case, then one only establishes conservation of energy at each point in space on average. As a result, for short time periods the energy may differ from E which seems to be related to the uncertainty principle $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \hbar$. In this note, we also examine the idea of averaging over time in classical statistical mechanics. It seems that averages here are also computed over time. If this is the case, then it seems that an uncertainty principle should also apply in this classical case. In this note, we also consider the idea of collective motion in a dilute gas with a potential at equilibrium.

Quantum Mechanics

It was shown in (1) that the time independent Schrodinger equation could be written as:

$$\left[\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} \sin(px) \right] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Here $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, $V(x)$ is the classical potential which exists at each point x and the first term is the average kinetic energy. Thus, there is energy conservation at each point x , but this still raises the question whether this average exists at each instant of time t . It was argued (2) that a particle with zitterbewegung has probability to exist over a region of space related to the wavelength. Thus, there is both some spatial and time uncertainty related to the particle. In the 2×2 matrix model (3), a particle moves backward and forwards while moving on average to the right with speed v . Thus, the idea of having a particle at x with velocity v at time t is an average concept. This is carried over when the particle is placed in a potential. The plane wave representing the particle (to model the 2×2 matrix model nature of the particle for example) is carried over when the particle is placed in a potential. The particle scatters at various points in the potential, at different times and the scattered waves represent the particle with probabilities to be within a wavelength (associated with $\sin(px)$) at different times. Thus, there is uncertainty in space and time in such a picture. Here, we consider the case of time. It was argued that $\exp(iEt)$ in the wavefunction has physical meaning with E representing the frequency with which the particle cycles from one momentum state to another in order to create the average in ((1)). Thus, one needs at least a time of $1/E$ in order to "see" the average kinetic energy realized. For times shorter than this, one could see different kinetic energy values and hence different overall energy values. Thus, it is argued that there is an inherent energy uncertainty due to averaging over time. As the time approaches $1/E$, the system would have cycled through the different

momentum values and the kinetic energy would be approaching an average value which together with the potential energy would yield an energy of E . Given that the total energy is E , the smallest time interval may be estimated as $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. In such a time interval, the error in E could be as large as E because there has been almost no time during which the average kinetic energy could be established.

Energy Density in Quantum and Classical Mechanics

In ((1)), it was shown that there is conservation of energy at each point in space if one waits for at least a time $1/E$. In quantum mechanics, one has a spatial density of $W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction for a bound state. Thus, there is an energy density $E W(x)W(x)$ at each point in space. This might seem to imply that energy is conserved overall and not at each point x , but ((1)) shows that one can have energy conservation at each point. This can be compared to classical mechanics for which $\text{kinetic energy} + V(x) = E$ at each point x . According to (4), one can write a spatial probability density as $dx/v(x)$ where v is the velocity which depends on x . In such a case, the energy density is $E dx/v(x)$, so energy density varies with x . Again, one might think that there is no energy conservation at each point x , but that is not the case. It should be noted that as the quantum mechanical energy eigenvalue becomes large, the spatial density of quantum mechanics approaches that of the classical one $dx/v(x)$, so there is a connection between the two.

Statistical Mechanics

In statistical mechanics, one again deals with averages and it seems that these may need to be taken over an interval of time. For example, consider a dilute gas whose particles only collide with the walls of a container at temperature T . The gas particles are said to follow a Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-KE/T)$ and are regulated by the wall. If one looks at a small portion of the wall, however, it seems that it will require a certain interval of time in which to see this distribution realized. That interval should be related to the temperature T as well as to length scales in the system, it seems. (If one considered only one particle colliding with the wall, the interval would be the cycling time for the different velocities to be created with a Boltzmann distribution.) As a result, the average energy of the gas and the Boltzmann distribution can only be established by taking measurements over this interval of time, just as in quantum mechanics. As a result, for intervals shorter than this characteristic cycling time, one may have uncertainties in energy, just as in the uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics.

Consider now the case of a spatial distribution of a dilute gas. The idea that there is a time interval required during which one can measure the Boltzmann distribution is in keeping with the idea that gas particles collide with a portion of the wall at different times. In addition, these particles scatter off the wall with different velocities, as governed by the Boltzmann distribution. On average, however, the average separation of particles in the gas must be a constant, otherwise the gas would not have a constant density. Next, consider adding a potential. This will give potential as well as kinetic energy to each particle in the dilute gas. The sum of the kinetic and potential energy will be a constant. Imagine that the potential is zero at both walls and

decreases towards the center. The gas particles will move according to classical mechanics, speeding up as they approach the center of the one dimensional space, then slowing down as they move toward a wall. Now there is collective as well as thermal velocity in the problem. The relative probabilities do not change as the Boltzmann factor is $\exp(-(\text{kinetic} + \text{potential energy})/T)$. In the center, however, the average kinetic energy is higher than $3/2 n(x)RT$, $n(x)$ being the density, from the thermal kinetic energy as there is additional collective motion. As gas particles are moving to both the right and left, there is collective flow energy in both directions. In general, this collective flow energy does not seem to be discussed when speaking of classical statistical averages. For example, one argues that for a little box at x , there is a density $n(x)$ of particles with thermal energy $3/2RT$ creating a pressure $PV=nRT$. The density $n(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. Thus, there is a pressure balance being described if one considers boxes at $x-\delta$, x and $x+\delta$. The pressure difference of the boxes at $x-\delta$ and $x+\delta$ balance the force $=-dV(x)/dx$ times the density at x . In such a picture, there does not seem to be any collective velocity at all, but it does seem to be present in the picture of a dilute gas (and also a dense gas). The idea of collective velocity seems to be important as one may have sound waves associated with collective fluid motion. Here there is collective in both directions and it is linked to the conservation of energy (kinetic energy + potential energy = E), but it is interesting to speculate the possible presence of sound type waves.)

One may ask why the spatial density of a dilute gas takes on the form $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. For the case of no potential, the average interparticle distance seems to be a constant. Given that the particles travel at different speeds, introducing a potential will accelerate the particles so that the average interparticle spacing changes. In a hand-wavy manner, one can consider a central region where there is a low potential energy and a high kinetic energy. In such a case, all particles obtain extra collective kinetic energy and achieve large speeds. In a small time interval, many particles can pass through a small box used for measuring density. In a region where the potential is high, and kinetic energy low, many particles will be moving slowly. In the same measuring time interval δt a smaller number of particles will pass through the box. Thus, the idea of conservation of energy at different points in space and the idea of collective velocity seem to be very important in classical statistical mechanics, even though these do not seem to appear in the static-looking densities. Again, an interval of time is required to establish averages and this interval seems to be related to temperature T as well as other factors.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that there is a cycling frequency in quantum mechanics, namely E from $\exp(iEt)$. This frequency, or its associated time, is important in establishing averages, such as an average kinetic energy at each point. If one does not take measurements over such an interval of time, one may obtain partial averages or in other words obtain energy uncertainty as in the energy time uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics. It seems that the same ideas of averaging over time apply to statistical classical mechanics. In the case of a dilute gas, it seems that one must take averages over a time interval related to temperature T in order to establish

the existence of the Boltzmann distribution. Taking an average over a shorter time, it seems would lead to possible uncertainties in energy like in the case of the quantum uncertainty principle.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. 2x2 Matrix Model and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Possible Relation Between Quantum Mechanical Cycling $\text{Exp}(iEt)$ and the Correspondence Principle and Physical Oscillating Objects Like Phonons and Photons (preprint, zenodo, 2018)
4. Majernick V and Opatiny Y. Entropic uncertainty in classical quantum Oscillator (J Phys A Math Gen, 1995, UK) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>